

An extensible software toolbox for the *in silico* optimization of aptamers towards arbitrarily complex objectives

Nikolaos I. Kalavros^{1,2,*}, George Tsekenis^{1,*}

¹ Basic Research Center, Biomedical Research Foundation of the Academy of Athens, Athens, Soranou Ephessiou 4, 115 27 Athens, Greece

² Department of Informatics and Telecommunications, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, Panepistimiopolis, Ilissia, Athens 157 84, Greece

* To whom correspondence should be addressed.

Nikolaos I. Kalavros: Tel: +30 6931972159; Fax: +30 6931972159; Email: nkalavros@di.uoa.gr

George Tsekenis: Tel: +30 6972662700; Fax: +30 6972662700; Email: gtsekenis@bioacademy.gr

Abstract:

Nucleic acid aptamers are a class of molecules that show great potential for a variety of applications, including biosensing, diagnostics and therapeutics. They are small molecules, with high affinity and specificity towards a particular ligand. The main method of aptamer identification is Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential Enrichment (SELEX), which was first described over three decades ago. Despite the fact that SELEX and the multitude of its variants have matured significantly since then, key difficulties remain, ranging from implementation issues to cross-reactivity of the aptamer with structurally similar ligands. Due to the vast search space of possible aptamer structures, which is only enlarged when accounting for other desired properties, *in silico* simulations are highly desirable. Herein, we present a toolbox that aims to simplify and accelerate computational aptamer characterization utilizing a wealth of tools for every step and integrating their findings to increase accuracy and realizing a sophisticated, extensible pipeline for aptamer refinement according to arbitrarily complex designs based on user-set criteria. We compare several tools and apply our workflow in various setting, likely to be encountered by practitioners and show that our algorithm can be very accurate in the prediction of aptamer - target binding affinities, as well as able to produce refined aptamer candidates for experimental validation. Finally, we consolidate all of the programs used in a unified containerized software solution that is very modular and can be readily deployed in any environment, equipped with an API and GUI that can abstract away the complexity of using and integrating the programs and help less programmatically experienced users add computational biology workflows to their methodologies.

Introduction:

Aptamers are small oligonucleotide or oligopeptide molecules that exhibit high affinity and high specificity to specific targets. Since their discovery, they have found widespread usage in the field of biosensors, biochemical applications and therapeutic ones. They are quite robust and their stability, small size¹, low batch-to-batch variability² and long shelf-life³, compared to antibodies, are highly desirable properties⁴.

The identification of aptamers is currently based on a screening process named Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential Enrichment (SELEX)^{5,6}, which through iterative amplification and washing of an initial randomized pool, flanked by known sequences which can be used for amplification, can lead to the discovery of promising aptamer candidates which can bind target molecules. As the non-binders are removed from the pool through washing, only the better binding sequences will be amplified, leading to the saturation of the library with few, usually less than 10, promising sequences. The pool is then sequenced to identify said candidates.

Several variants of SELEX have been proposed over the years⁷, increasing throughput, reducing the time needed⁸, or displaying the ligand and/or aptamer in different ways, such as on beads⁹, in live cells^{10,11}, or even in living organisms^{12,13}. However, SELEX and its variants' adoption is hampered by the needed cost of infrastructure, for high throughput (e.g. microfluidics, *in vivo*), reagent requirements and time¹⁴.

Given their slew of applications and the laborious/costly protocols involved, methods that can identify aptamers *in silico*¹⁵ or rank them¹⁶⁻¹⁹ are highly desirable. Many such methods have been described in the literature²⁰⁻²⁴ and have been reviewed elsewhere^{25,26}. Most of these methods employ common steps, such as nucleic acid secondary structure prediction, nucleic acid tertiary structure prediction, docking and molecular dynamics (MD) simulations. These prediction methods are especially important when no 3D structure of the aptamer-ligand complex is available, which is true in the majority of cases. While such methods introduce progressively larger, compounding errors in the final results, they are being constantly refined through the release of new and improved software²⁷⁻³⁰. Despite the apparent limitations, computational methods have been successful both the *de novo* identification of aptamers binding to a specific ligand and in refining already existing ones³¹.

In tandem with methods that aim to identify aptamers, methodologies that can accurately predict the secondary and tertiary structure of nucleic acids have been improved immensely. Furthermore, in the vein of CASP³² and CAPRI³³, competitions and benchmarks have been created for RNA secondary³⁴ and tertiary structure prediction³⁵ and RNA - protein docking³⁶. A special mention should be made for deep learning based methods, which have been outperforming other methodologies in several fields, such as RNA 3D structure ranking³⁷⁻³⁹ and protein 3D structure prediction⁴⁰ and have begun appearing in the computational aptamer field as well⁴¹⁻⁴³. While extremely promising, these methods require the prior existence of data, which is scarce⁴⁴, especially compared to proteins, according to the PDB⁴⁵ and the experimental determination of DNA or RNA 3D structure is notoriously difficult⁴⁶.

Motivated by the advent of automated software, greatly limiting the need for expert input, we sought to create an all-in-one pipeline that can facilitate the characterization and refinement of existing aptamers by taking advantage of existing software. In this effort, we consolidated a vast array of existing programs in the literature under a unified Python API, abstracting away the difficulties of deploying each one separately and strived for modularity by using containerization software, as well as virtual environments, if containerization itself is not readily available.

For aptamer refinement, we formulated the problem as an iterative optimization algorithm, where an aptamer is mutated by passing it through a pre-defined probability matrix that defines the probability of each mutation, addition or deletion taking place and then scored. The term scored is purposefully left vague, as the scoring function can take various forms, depending on the user's need but it often relates to the binding affinity of the aptamer towards a target. This score can be based on a docking scoring function, as well as any other score and any mathematical operations in between. In typical Genetic Algorithm fashion, the mutation matrix is used to generate descendants of a sequence and they, along with their predecessor are scored and the top k candidates (according to the score) are kept.

This study also serves as a small benchmark study of pipelines that can generate a 3D structure from a nucleic acid sequence and we perform ablation-like analyses to assess which parts of the sequence -> 3D structure pipeline are most important for accurate docking. Naive integration methodologies are also implemented in order to utilize more than one program during the sequence -> 3D structure pipeline. Furthermore, we integrate MD analyses in order to more saliently characterize aptamer - target interactions.

Materials and Methods:

Computational aptamer characterization:

The basic steps of the computational characterization of an aptamer can be broadly categorized as follows; Given an nucleic acid aptamer sequence, compute its secondary structure, utilize said structure to predict its tertiary structure, which is instrumental for aptamer – target interactions. If the target structure is not known a priori, it is also computed at this step. Then, perform docking to generate binding poses, the best of which will be utilized as input for MD simulations. Of course, given the multitude of tools to perform each of the above steps, there is no best method to follow. Also, the workflow described here is feasible and functional, but quite naive in nature. In our proposed pipeline, we expand upon the above methodology, which has been used in literature, both by increasing the number of tools utilized in each step and by introducing refinement steps in between the main steps listed here.

More specifically, we utilize 10 programs for RNA secondary structure prediction, the outputs of which can be combined and refined using already existing methods. In addition to those, there are interfaces to specialized structure prediction software for pseudoknots and G-quadruplexes, which can help inform tertiary structure prediction in ways that other programs are unable to. Concomitantly, we utilize 5 methods for RNA tertiary structure prediction, as well as 3 methods for RNA to DNA conversion and 2 methodologies for NA structure refinement. These steps are especially important, as most programs that predict

tertiary structure were designed with RNA in mind. The RNA to DNA conversion is sure to introduce noise to the predicted model and we reason, therefore, that refinement is necessary. We have also incorporated a very recent methodology that can gauge the accuracy of a tertiary structure. Once more, tertiary structure prediction programs' results are integrated to generate one structure, which is then subject to docking, along with the ligand, utilizing 7 different docking programs. The results are scored both according to the internal scoring function of the program and a recently published alternative method which has been shown to be able to distinguish near native poses, using a tailor-made score function. The top poses are selected for downstream analysis and examination. Finally, two different MD engines can be used to conduct simulations starting from the best binding poses, with additional functionality for Absolute Binding Free Energy calculations, according to several well established algorithms. To aid in the interpretation of the data, several plotting and visualization related functions have been implemented, making examination intuitive and easy. The implemented methodologies are summarized in Table 1 and described in detail in the Supplementary Material.

We elected to use container runtimes to enhance the modularity of the software and allow for deployment in any kind of environment that supports them, with or without admin execution privileges. Both an Application Programming Interface (API) and an intuitive Graphical User Interface (GUI) were also created, implemented in the Python programming language, in an effort to help users less experienced in coding with the use of the software, while empowering power users to be able to abstract away the need for laborious installation by abstracting away everything under the API. Liberal use of parallelization is made, controllable by user defined flags, in order to accelerate computation. For MD simulations especially, Graphical Processing Units (GPUs) can be utilized for acceleration. Lastly, sample scripts have also been created that can automate the submission of jobs to shared HPC environments, using SLURM. The toolbox is also under active development, in order to implement more tools, such as the simulations of modified nucleosides or the addition of protein aptamers.

Aptamer refinement as an optimization problem:

We and several others have developed methodologies to computationally characterize an aptamer's binding affinity towards its target. It is very straightforward to leverage such a pipeline to facilitate a process of iterative aptamer refinement and there are several avenues to do so. The approach that we elected to follow here is a Genetic Algorithm (GA). In general terms, given an aptamer sequence, said sequence is mutated, using a pre-defined mutation matrix into new sequences, which are all evaluated based on a scoring function. The best performing of those new sequences are then allowed to "procreate", mutating or crossing over to generate new sequences, which are then also evaluated. This process can iteratively continue, leading to monotonic increase (or

decrease) to the scoring function's value. In this particular case, the scoring function takes as input a sequence and can return a binding affinity value (either the output of one of the docking programs, or an MD estimated binding free energy value). The number of generations, children sequences and number of top candidates selected per generation can all be defined beforehand by the user or in some cases, adaptively computed, using a patience value. In the patience value approach, a value ΔScore is selected, as well as a number of generations P . If the scoring function has not increased by ΔScore in P generations, the algorithm halts.

Further mention should be given to the scoring function, as it is finally the function that governs which sequences will be chosen for the next generation. While naive function may prove very useful in many cases (e.g. $-\Delta G$ – the increase of binding affinity), more sophisticated functions can be crafted by the user, to achieve the desired example. A prime example that directly adds to the simplistic “binding affinity” scoring function is the “specific binding affinity” scoring function ($\text{Score} = -\Delta G_1 + \kappa \Delta G_2$), which aims to increase the binding affinity of an aptamer to target 1, while decreasing the binding affinity towards target 2, which could be a similar, confounding structure. The complexity of the scoring function can be arbitrary, limited by the needs of the simulation. For example, since binding poses are output as PDB files, users may require that a part of the aptamer be extra rigid, using its RMSD against a reference structure in the score or that the target should bind in a specific site of the aptamer, utilizing the distance of the target's center of mass to the center of mass of the binding site. Several examples of scoring functions are provided in the Supplementary Material.

The sequence of programs used to arrive at the scoring function is also up to the user, though sensible default pipelines have been implemented. For instance, if a user needs a “quick and dirty” simulation, they might elect not to use all programs and integrate findings, but rather, one fast program per step that performs well for similar use cases, based on experience and intuition. Similarly, if GPUs are not available and MD simulations are prohibitively slow, users may opt for a scoring function that is based solely on steps up to docking, which is far faster and easily parallelizable to Central Processing Units (CPUs). Such freedom allows the user to customize the pipeline completely to their needs, as well as the expended computational resources.

Results:

Construction of a diverse aptamer - target dataset

In an effort to benchmark currently existing tools for aptamer - target interactions, we sought to gather a dataset of high confidence pairs from existing literature. Querying the PDB, X high confidence complexes were selected based on the following criteria:

- Diversity in target pairs (small molecules, protein fragments, whole proteins)
- Diversity in nucleic acids (length, DNA/RNA, structural features)
- Good resolution

The aptamers selected through this process are described in Table 2. While this list is by no means exhaustive, it presents a reasonable challenge for most combinations of tools and more are currently being added.

Assessing each tool on different settings

Aiming to simulate real world scenarios, we tested each different combination of tools on this small-scale test dataset of 5 aptamer - target complexes. The first scenario is when no prior information, other than the aptamer sequence and ligand are available. This is termed as the Blind [B] scenario. The next scenarios are closely related and include the scenario where the secondary structure of the aptamer is known, which could be probed using CD⁴⁷, chemical mapping such as SHAPE⁴⁸, or other similar techniques, termed Secondary [S]. Accordingly, the scenario where the tertiary structure of the aptamer is known is termed Tertiary [T], which could reasonably be obtained through NMR⁴⁹ or X-Ray Diffraction⁵⁰. Similarly, researchers may have had knowledge of putative binding sites on the receptor, through similar experiments, which have long been used for both small molecules⁵¹ and proteins⁵². This scenario was termed Knowledge [K]. Finally, in order to benchmark the target structure prediction programs, a final scenario was created, named Ligand [L]. Structures for targets of interest can be reasonably obtained from existing databases, such as the PDB⁴⁵, or the CSD⁵³. Of course, a scenario where all structures are known *a priori*, termed All [A] was also created.

Depending on the scenario being tested, different metrics were employed to rank the programs. Based on the large scale EternaFold study⁵⁴, we used Arnie⁵⁵ to compare secondary structure prediction methods and created appropriate script for methods that were not included. To assess accuracy on the level of 3D structure, we adopted metrics from the RNA Puzzles IV study³⁵, namely, RMSD and Clash⁵⁶ against the native structure. For ligand structure prediction evaluation, we used the RMSD to the native structure, as done in similar publications for small molecules⁵⁷ and RMSD as well for proteins specifically. To constrain the exponential search space and accompanying computational costs, currently a subset of the total program combinations has been investigated. Additionally, for programs that produce multiple predictions (e.g. multiple conformers, RNA structures, binding poses), only the top 3 were tested.

Our results largely recapitulate previous findings for small nucleic acid structure prediction, as shown in Figure 1. Most tertiary RNA structure prediction programs provide reasonably good reasonable structures with low clash scores and good RMSD values in most cases and the secondary structure prediction programs largely agree for small aptamers. It should be noted that some methods suffer from high clash scores if no refinement steps are utilized. It remains to be seen how well this can translate to larger aptamers, which have long been a very difficult issue to tackle in the field. Some trends do emerge however. Structure prediction becomes generally less accurate with increased length, as well as complexity, and the canonical secondary structure can be predicted quite accurately for small nucleic acids. While in most cases, the produced structure's RMSD is quite low, it cannot be ruled out that structure prediction programs output an energetically favourable structure, which is different to the solved one.

As for the docked complex itself, from a combination of 6 secondary structure prediction programs (ViennaRNA, NUPACK, ContraFold, EternaFold, BPRNA, RNASoft), 4 tertiary structure prediction programs (SimRNA, 3dRNA2.0, RNAComposer, FARFAR2), 2 different ligand structure prediction software (RDKit and OpenBabel) and 6 docking programs (Vina, RxDock, iDock, HADDOCK, DOCK6 and ZDOCK) queried for the 5 aptamers used here, the complex heavy atom RMSD to the reference structure varies. Methods that included FARFAR2 and either AutoDock Vina or RxDock consistently outputted complexes with RMSD lower than 5Å, which while not as close to native as one would conventionally like (<2 Å), are acceptable as initial poses for MD simulation.

We also sought to investigate what happens when there is more information regarding the aptamer target complex. As one would expect, knowledge of tertiary structure beforehand (docking to the apo structure of the complex, rather than a predicted one) has the most pronounced effect on the final RMSD, whereas due to, in part, the nature of the dataset, prior secondary structure knowledge plays a negligible role, as seen in Figure 3. Regrettably, while prior knowledge of the tertiary structure plays the biggest role, it is also the hardest one to obtain.

The integrative approach described in this publication performs reasonably well for most datasets, failing when only a minority of methods produces good results. In the integrative method, for each step, the program with the least average RMSD (or Hamming Distance for secondary structure) against the other programs used in the same step is chosen. This can help accelerate the process by greedily choosing a program at each step, instead of running all combinations combinatorially.

Given these findings, we believe that sensible default choices can be made, such as a methodology consisting of: EternaFold → FARFAR2 → QRNAS → Vina, using Rdkit for the ligand with a runtime of less than 1 core hour per aptamer - ligand sequence (in SMILES notation), in order to increase speed, there is no method that always outperforms the others in a pipeline that attempts to computationally elucidate the mechanisms of an aptamer - target complex. As such, despite the increased computational overhead, efforts should be made to include more than one program for each step of the process and develop methodologies to integrate results from several programs. Our approach is a first, albeit naive step, in such a direction.

Optimizing already existing aptamer sequences towards a target

Bolstered by the performance of the tool combinations on the small scale test dataset, we sought generated complexes from other aptamers of interest, where known ones were not available. We chose 3 very important antibiotics, which have aptamers that are well documented in the literature, namely PenG, an antibiotic that is widely used in dairy products and whose detection in said products is critical in order to combat strains that develop resistance to it, AFM1 for similar reasons and Neomycin, another antibiotic widely used in the food industry which also has very strict residue limitations in products in the EU[ref]. While several aptamers for each of these compounds do exist and they have been extensively characterized with regards to their binding affinity, said aptamers have not been tested computationally and any optimization efforts are based on laborious, experimental trial and error based assays.

We adopted the integrative approach that also produced reasonable results in the test dataset and formulated a Genetic Algorithm whose objective function was the negative of the docking score (ΔG or otherwise) of the aptamer and the ligand, as described in the Methods section. Each run consisted of 10 candidates per generation and 15 generations were run for each aptamer - target pair.

As shown in Figure 4, even after a few generations, there is a noted decrease in the binding ΔG of the aptamer and the ligand (equivalent to an increase in the score function), which starts to plateau as generations increase. The algorithm terminated on its own once the patience threshold had been exceeded. In most cases, the binding site itself was not changed excessively, but the aptamer bases interacting with the target were, favouring sequences with more well defined and stable secondary structures.

Characterizing aptamer - target complexes using Molecular Dynamics Simulations

While docking software has been consistently improving over the years, it is usually inadvisable to use the score outputted by said software as an estimate of binding free energy and more sophisticated approaches should be employed to get more accurate ΔG . Luckily, poses suggested by docking can be used as initial conformations for MD simulations. In this step too, multiple methodologies were used to estimate the binding ΔG of the aptamer with its target, both before and after refinement. Each methodology presents a different trade-off between speed and accuracy and as such, we wished to gauge whether we could reduce needed computational resources by utilizing the faster methods. After correct parametrization, both alchemical and geometric methods can be used to reliably estimate ΔG , but such parameterization is not trivial to implement and usually requires trial and error, as has been repeatedly noted in the literature[ref]. The end-point methods are faster and easier to implement, but their estimates are consistently worse. Details on the workflow followed for MD simulations can be found in the Supplementary Material.

Briefly, promising binding poses were selected based on their score and parameterized using the ff14SB force field for nucleic acids with the BL1 and OL3 correction, as well as the GAFF2 forcefield for small molecules and solvated in a 12A dodecahedron of TIP3P water. A short minimization of 10000 thousand steps, 5000 steps of conjugated gradient and 5000 of steepest descent. This was followed by a gradual heating over 2 ns and a slow NVT equilibration of another 2 and an NPT equilibration of 2 ns, after which, 100 ns of production MD were performed. ABFE calculations were performed using TI, with a 16 lambda window scheme and 5 ns in each lambda, until the complete annihilation of the ligand and a polynomial curve was fitted to calculate the ΔG from the dV/dL through integration. Simulations were run both for the initial aptamer - target complexes and for the optimized ones.

The MD simulations perform very well in the estimation of ΔG , always being within 1.5 kcal/mol of the true one and while a case for a trend of overestimation of binding affinity through MD can be seen, no concrete case can be made with such a small dataset. The optimized aptamer structures do show improvement, but it should be noted that since it is not substantial improvement in terms of ΔG and given that ABFE simulations might have a

margin of error of even 2 kcal/mol, more drastic ΔG changes would need to be observed before an unequivocal claim of improvement can be made.

Discussion:

In recent years, great strides have been made in incorporating computational methods to both enhance and accelerate experimental workflows, by pruning the number of experiments that need to be performed before a successful one. In fact, methods for the in silico design of proteins of desired backbones, pipelines for the *de novo* creation of proteins based on deep learning architectures which have been shown to have incredible accuracy and methodologies aimed to predict the accuracy of RNA structures have been described very recently. Computational methods' development is intimately related with experimental methods development, as the experimental methods serve as the validation data and incorporation of larger continuously larger datasets when developing new computational methodologies, especially in the field of machine learning.

However, the field of aptamers does not yet utilize the wealth of these methodologies, which, in our opinion, comes down to two reasons. The first is the ease of adoption, which has been shown to affect computational tool use in other disciplines. In fact, since the target audience for such pipelines is not only computational biologists, but experimentalists, programs must spare no effort in making the software easy to install and easy to use. The second one is the lack of a golden standard, or other benchmarking studies specifically focused on aptamers, which make researchers reluctant to adopt said tools, in fear of them producing spurious results. Since there is a breadth of tools, each with its own advantages and disadvantages, making this choice more intuitive for researchers is also of high priority.

In our toolbox, we aimed to address both of these problems. By gathering a multitude of tools in one, integrated package, which abstracts away the need to write specialized code for each tool under a unified Python API, as well as creating a user interface for novice users and packaging the toolbox as a container to increase modularity, we hope to render our tool more easily adoptable for the wider community. Furthermore, we have adopted methods to integrate the results from many different programs[ref] and to produce interpretable results at each step, so researchers can evaluate process in real time and choose their preferred set of tools.

Additionally, through constructing a small scale test dataset, comparisons between different tools for each step can be made. As we've shown, there is no "best" tool, something that is true for most disciplines and the corresponding tools. However, there are many tools which produce results that are very close to experimentally measured ones. Some inferences can be made based on the data shown here. First, no method works very well for very large aptamers yet. As few solved nucleic acid structures exist[ref], training a method that would work for large ones is a rather difficult task[ref]. Furthermore, complex structures are quite difficult to correctly predict (pseudoknots, quadruplexes) and the creation of pipelines that include specialized

software made to predict such structural elements may alleviate this issue. Finally, in most cases, special care should be taken to ensure the correct parametrization of MD simulations.

Finally, through the API, complex optimization schemes can be constructed for aptamer candidates and by changing the underlying objective function, researchers can fit the pipeline into their own studies, investigating only what's necessary and avoiding needless computational costs.

Understandably, such results are not yet conclusive, as we're still in the process of experimentally validating the results for several of our examples and will update this preprint accordingly once submitted.

Data and Source code Availability:

All data generated in this study, as well as the source code and installation scripts will be made available upon publication. Note that the licenses for the programs' usage will need to be obtained by the user.

Conflict of Interest:

N.K. and G.T. are involved in an ongoing patent application relating to Aptamer optimization through computational methods.

References:

1. Zhou, J. & Rossi, J. Aptamers as targeted therapeutics: current potential and challenges. *Nat. Rev. Drug Discov.* **16**, 181–202 (2017).
2. Bauer, M., Strom, M., Hammond, D. S. & Shigdar, S. Anything You Can Do, I Can Do Better: Can Aptamers Replace Antibodies in Clinical Diagnostic Applications? *Molecules* **24**, 4377 (2019).
3. Wang, T., Chen, C., Larcher, L. M., Barrero, R. A. & Veedu, R. N. Three decades of nucleic acid aptamer technologies: Lessons learned, progress and opportunities on aptamer development. *Biotechnol. Adv.* **37**, 28–50 (2019).
4. Komarova, N. & Kuznetsov, A. Inside the Black Box: What Makes SELEX Better? *Molecules* **24**, 3598 (2019).
5. Tuerk, C. & Gold, L. Systematic Evolution of Ligands by Exponential Enrichment: RNA Ligands to Bacteriophage T4 DNA Polymerase. *Science* **249**, 505–510 (1990).
6. Ellington, A. D. & Szostak, J. W. In vitro selection of RNA molecules that bind specific ligands. *Nature* **346**, 818–822 (1990).
7. Introduction of SELEX and Important SELEX Variants - Aptamers for Analytical Applications - Wiley Online Library.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/9783527806799.ch1>.
8. Olsen, T. *et al.* AN INTEGRATED MICROFLUIDIC SELEX APPROACH USING COMBINED ELECTROKINETIC AND HYDRODYNAMIC MANIPULATION. *SLAS Technol.* **22**, 63–72 (2017).
9. Lyu, C., Khan, I. M. & Wang, Z. Capture-SELEX for aptamer selection: A short review. *Talanta* **229**, 122274 (2021).
10. Sefah, K., Shangguan, D., Xiong, X., O'Donoghue, M. B. & Tan, W. Development of DNA aptamers using Cell-SELEX. *Nat. Protoc.* **5**, 1169–1185 (2010).
11. Kaur, H. Recent developments in cell-SELEX technology for aptamer selection. *Biochim. Biophys. Acta Gen. Subj.* **1862**, 2323–2329 (2018).

12. Wang, H. *et al.* In Vivo SELEX of an Inhibitory NSCLC-Specific RNA Aptamer from PEGylated RNA Library. *Mol. Ther. Nucleic Acids* **10**, 187–198 (2017).
13. Aptamers Against Live Targets: Is In Vivo SELEX Finally Coming to the Edge?:
Molecular Therapy - Nucleic Acids.
[https://www.cell.com/molecular-therapy-family/nucleic-acids/fulltext/S2162-2531\(20\)30151-7](https://www.cell.com/molecular-therapy-family/nucleic-acids/fulltext/S2162-2531(20)30151-7).
14. Liu, H. & Yu, J. Challenges of SELEX and Demerits of Aptamer-Based Methods. in *Aptamers for Analytical Applications* 345–364 (John Wiley & Sons, Ltd, 2018).
doi:10.1002/9783527806799.ch12.
15. Platt, M. *et al.* Aptamer evolution for array-based diagnostics. *Anal. Biochem.* **390**, 203–205 (2009).
16. Caroli, J., Taccioli, C., De La Fuente, A., Serafini, P. & Bicciato, S. APTANI: a computational tool to select aptamers through sequence-structure motif analysis of HT-SELEX data. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **32**, 161–164 (2016).
17. Caroli, J., Forcato, M. & Bicciato, S. APTANI2: update of aptamer selection through sequence-structure analysis. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 2266–2268 (2020).
18. Ishida, R. *et al.* RaptRanker: in silico RNA aptamer selection from HT-SELEX experiment based on local sequence and structure information. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **48**, e82 (2020).
19. Shieh, K. R. *et al.* AptCompare: optimized de novo motif discovery of RNA aptamers via HTS-SELEX. *Bioinformatics* **36**, 2905–2906 (2020).
20. Bell, D. R. *et al.* In silico design and validation of high-affinity RNA aptamers targeting epithelial cellular adhesion molecule dimers. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* **117**, 8486–8493 (2020).
21. Rhinehardt, K. L., Mohan, R. V. & Srinivas, G. Computational modeling of peptide-aptamer binding. *Methods Mol. Biol. Clifton NJ* **1268**, 313–333 (2015).
22. Ahirwar, R. *et al.* In silico selection of an aptamer to estrogen receptor alpha using computational docking employing estrogen response elements as aptamer-alike

- molecules. *Sci. Rep.* **6**, 21285 (2016).
23. Campos-Fernández, E., Barcelos, L. S., Souza, A. G., Goulart, L. R. & Alonso-Goulart, V. Post-SELEX Optimization and Characterization of a Prostate Cancer Cell-Specific Aptamer for Diagnosis. *ACS Omega* **5**, 3533–3541 (2020).
 24. Lee, G., Jang, G. H., Kang, H. Y. & Song, G. Predicting aptamer sequences that interact with target proteins using an aptamer-protein interaction classifier and a Monte Carlo tree search approach. *PLOS ONE* **16**, e0253760 (2021).
 25. Buglak, A. A., Samokhvalov, A. V., Zherdev, A. V. & Dzantiev, B. B. Methods and Applications of In Silico Aptamer Design and Modeling. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **21**, E8420 (2020).
 26. Kinghorn, A. B., Fraser, L. A., Liang, S., Shiu, S. C.-C. & Tanner, J. A. Aptamer Bioinformatics. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **18**, 2516 (2017).
 27. Phillips, J. C. *et al.* Scalable molecular dynamics on CPU and GPU architectures with NAMD. *J. Chem. Phys.* **153**, 044130 (2020).
 28. Lee, T.-S. *et al.* Alchemical Binding Free Energy Calculations in AMBER20: Advances and Best Practices for Drug Discovery. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **60**, 5595–5623 (2020).
 29. Bonomi, M. *et al.* Promoting transparency and reproducibility in enhanced molecular simulations. *Nat. Methods* **16**, 670–673 (2019).
 30. Abraham, M. J. *et al.* GROMACS: High performance molecular simulations through multi-level parallelism from laptops to supercomputers. *SoftwareX* **1–2**, 19–25 (2015).
 31. Jeddi, I. & Saiz, L. Three-dimensional modeling of single stranded DNA hairpins for aptamer-based biosensors. *Sci. Rep.* **7**, 1178 (2017).
 32. High-accuracy protein structure prediction in CASP14 - Pereira - - Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics - Wiley Online Library.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/prot.26171>.
 33. Modeling protein-protein, protein-peptide, and protein-oligosaccharide complexes: CAPRI 7th edition - Lensink - 2020 - Proteins: Structure, Function, and Bioinformatics - Wiley Online Library. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/prot.25870>.

34. Wayment-Steele, H. K. *et al.* RNA secondary structure packages evaluated and improved by high-throughput experiments. 2020.05.29.124511
<https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.05.29.124511v2> (2021)
doi:10.1101/2020.05.29.124511.
35. RNA-Puzzles Round IV: 3D structure predictions of four ribozymes and two aptamers.
<https://rnajournal.cshlp.org/content/early/2020/05/05/rna.075341.120>.
36. Nithin, C., Mukherjee, S. & Bahadur, R. P. A non-redundant protein-RNA docking benchmark version 2.0. *Proteins* **85**, 256–267 (2017).
37. Li, J. & Chen, S.-J. RNA 3D Structure Prediction Using Coarse-Grained Models. *Front. Mol. Biosci.* **8**, 623 (2021).
38. Townshend, R. J. L. *et al.* Geometric deep learning of RNA structure. *Science* **373**, 1047–1051 (2021).
39. Li, B., Cao, Y., Westhof, E. & Miao, Z. Advances in RNA 3D Structure Modeling Using Experimental Data. *Front. Genet.* **11**, 1147 (2020).
40. Jumper, J. *et al.* Highly accurate protein structure prediction with AlphaFold. *Nature* **596**, 583–589 (2021).
41. Bashir, A. *et al.* Machine learning guided aptamer refinement and discovery. *Nat. Commun.* **12**, 2366 (2021).
42. Emami, N. & Ferdousi, R. AptaNet as a deep learning approach for aptamer–protein interaction prediction. *Sci. Rep.* **11**, 6074 (2021).
43. Chen, Z. *et al.* Artificial Intelligence in Aptamer–Target Binding Prediction. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **22**, 3605 (2021).
44. Schlick, T. & Pyle, A. M. Opportunities and Challenges in RNA Structural Modeling and Design. *Biophys. J.* **113**, 225–234 (2017).
45. Berman, H. M. *et al.* The Protein Data Bank. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **28**, 235–242 (2000).
46. Sabri, M. Z., Hamid, A. A. A., Hitam, S. M. S. & Rahim, Mohd. Z. A. The assessment of three dimensional modelling design for single strand DNA aptamers for computational chemistry application. *Biophys. Chem.* **267**, 106492 (2020).

47. Bishop, G. R. & Chaires, J. B. Characterization of DNA structures by circular dichroism. *Curr. Protoc. Nucleic Acid Chem.* **Chapter 7**, Unit 7.11 (2003).
48. Low, J. T. & Weeks, K. M. SHAPE-directed RNA secondary structure prediction. *Methods* **52**, 150–158 (2010).
49. Al-Hashimi, H. M. NMR studies of nucleic acid dynamics. *J. Magn. Reson. San Diego Calif 1997* **237**, 191–204 (2013).
50. Zhang, W., Szostak, J. W. & Huang, Z. Nucleic acid crystallization and X-ray crystallography facilitated by single selenium atom. *Front. Chem. Sci. Eng.* **10**, 196–202 (2016).
51. Pollard, T. D. A Guide to Simple and Informative Binding Assays. *Mol. Biol. Cell* **21**, 4061–4067 (2010).
52. Ludington, J. L. Protein Binding Site Analysis for Drug Discovery Using a Computational Fragment-Based Method. in *Fragment-Based Methods in Drug Discovery* (ed. Klon, A. E.) 145–154 (Springer, 2015). doi:10.1007/978-1-4939-2486-8_12.
53. Groom, C. R., Bruno, I. J., Lightfoot, M. P. & Ward, S. C. The Cambridge Structural Database. *Acta Crystallogr. Sect. B Struct. Sci. Cryst. Eng. Mater.* **72**, 171–179 (2016).
54. Wayment-Steele, H. K., Kladwang, W., Participants, E. & Das, R. *RNA secondary structure packages ranked and improved by high-throughput experiments*. 2020.05.29.124511 <https://www.biorxiv.org/content/10.1101/2020.05.29.124511v1> (2020) doi:10.1101/2020.05.29.124511.
55. *arnie*. (Das Lab, 2021).
56. Chen, V. B. *et al.* MolProbity: all-atom structure validation for macromolecular crystallography. *Acta Crystallogr. D Biol. Crystallogr.* **66**, 12–21 (2010).
57. Yoshikawa, N. & Hutchison, G. R. Fast, efficient fragment-based coordinate generation for Open Babel. *J. Cheminformatics* **11**, 49 (2019).
58. Lorenz, R. *et al.* ViennaRNA Package 2.0. *Algorithms Mol. Biol.* **6**, 26 (2011).
59. NUPACK: Analysis and design of nucleic acid systems - Zadeh - 2011 - Journal of Computational Chemistry - Wiley Online Library.

<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/full/10.1002/jcc.21596>.

60. Reuter, J. S. & Mathews, D. H. RNAstructure: software for RNA secondary structure prediction and analysis. *BMC Bioinformatics* **11**, 129 (2010).
61. Danaee, P. *et al.* bpRNA: large-scale automated annotation and analysis of RNA secondary structure. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **46**, 5381–5394 (2018).
62. Do, C. B., Woods, D. A. & Batzoglou, S. CONTRAfold: RNA secondary structure prediction without physics-based models. *Bioinforma. Oxf. Engl.* **22**, e90-8 (2006).
63. Andronescu, M., Zhang, Z. C. & Condon, A. Secondary structure prediction of interacting RNA molecules. *J. Mol. Biol.* **345**, 987–1001 (2005).
64. Zakov, S., Goldberg, Y., Elhadad, M. & Ziv-ukelson, M. Rich Parameterization Improves RNA Structure Prediction. *J. Comput. Biol.* **18**, 1525–1542 (2011).
65. Sato, K., Kato, Y., Hamada, M., Akutsu, T. & Asai, K. IPknot: fast and accurate prediction of RNA secondary structures with pseudoknots using integer programming. *Bioinformatics* **27**, i85–i93 (2011).
66. Sato, K., Hamada, M., Asai, K. & Mituyama, T. CentroidFold: a web server for RNA secondary structure prediction. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **37**, W277–W280 (2009).
67. Singh, J., Hanson, J., Paliwal, K. & Zhou, Y. RNA secondary structure prediction using an ensemble of two-dimensional deep neural networks and transfer learning. *Nat. Commun.* **10**, 5407 (2019).
68. Zuker, M. Mfold web server for nucleic acid folding and hybridization prediction. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **31**, 3406–3415 (2003).
69. Kikin, O., D'Antonio, L. & Bagga, P. S. QGRS Mapper: a web-based server for predicting G-quadruplexes in nucleotide sequences. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **34**, W676–W682 (2006).
70. Hon, J., Martínek, T., Zendulka, J. & Lexa, M. pqsfinder: an exhaustive and imperfection-tolerant search tool for potential quadruplex-forming sequences in R. *Bioinformatics* **33**, 3373–3379 (2017).
71. Lu, X.-J. & Olson, W. K. 3DNA: a versatile, integrated software system for the analysis, rebuilding and visualization of three-dimensional nucleic-acid structures. *Nat. Protoc.* **3**,

- 1213–1227 (2008).
72. Lu, X.-J. DSSR-enabled innovative schematics of 3D nucleic acid structures with PyMOL. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **48**, e74 (2020).
 73. Ropp, P. J. *et al.* Gypsum-DL: an open-source program for preparing small-molecule libraries for structure-based virtual screening. *J. Cheminformatics* **11**, 34 (2019).
 74. Landrum, G. RDKit: A software suite for cheminformatics, computational chemistry, and predictive modeling. 31.
 75. Biesiada, M., Purzycka, K. J., Szachniuk, M., Blazewicz, J. & Adamiak, R. W. Automated RNA 3D Structure Prediction with RNAComposer. *Methods Mol. Biol. Clifton NJ* **1490**, 199–215 (2016).
 76. Boniecki, M. J. *et al.* SimRNA: a coarse-grained method for RNA folding simulations and 3D structure prediction. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **44**, e63 (2016).
 77. Wang, J., Wang, J., Huang, Y. & Xiao, Y. 3dRNA v2.0: An Updated Web Server for RNA 3D Structure Prediction. *Int. J. Mol. Sci.* **20**, 4116 (2019).
 78. Watkins, A. M., Rangan, R. & Das, R. FARFAR2: Improved De Novo Rosetta Prediction of Complex Global RNA Folds. *Structure* **28**, 963-976.e6 (2020).
 79. Poblete, S., Bottaro, S. & Bussi, G. A nucleobase-centered coarse-grained representation for structure prediction of RNA motifs. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **46**, 1674–1683 (2018).
 80. Alford, R. F. *et al.* The Rosetta All-Atom Energy Function for Macromolecular Modeling and Design. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **13**, 3031–3048 (2017).
 81. Humphrey, W., Dalke, A. & Schulten, K. VMD: Visual molecular dynamics. *J. Mol. Graph.* **14**, 33–38 (1996).
 82. Pettersen, E. F. *et al.* UCSF Chimera—A visualization system for exploratory research and analysis. *J. Comput. Chem.* **25**, 1605–1612 (2004).
 83. Stasiewicz, J., Mukherjee, S., Nithin, C. & Bujnicki, J. M. QRNAS: software tool for refinement of nucleic acid structures. *BMC Struct. Biol.* **19**, 5 (2019).
 84. Case, D. A. *et al.* The Amber biomolecular simulation programs. *J. Comput. Chem.* **26**,

- 1668–1688 (2005).
85. Eberhardt, J., Santos-Martins, D., Tillack, A. F. & Forli, S. AutoDock Vina 1.2.0: New Docking Methods, Expanded Force Field, and Python Bindings. *J. Chem. Inf. Model.* **61**, 3891–3898 (2021).
 86. Pierce, B. G. *et al.* ZDOCK server: interactive docking prediction of protein–protein complexes and symmetric multimers. *Bioinformatics* **30**, 1771–1773 (2014).
 87. Li, H., Leung, K.-S. & Wong, M.-H. idock: A multithreaded virtual screening tool for flexible ligand docking. in *2012 IEEE Symposium on Computational Intelligence in Bioinformatics and Computational Biology (CIBCB)* 77–84 (2012).
doi:10.1109/CIBCB.2012.6217214.
 88. Sun, L.-Z., Jiang, Y., Zhou, Y. & Chen, S.-J. RLDOCK: A New Method for Predicting RNA–Ligand Interactions. *J. Chem. Theory Comput.* **16**, 7173–7183 (2020).
 89. Yan, Y., Tao, H., He, J. & Huang, S.-Y. The HDock server for integrated protein–protein docking. *Nat. Protoc.* **15**, 1829–1852 (2020).
 90. He, J., Wang, J., Tao, H., Xiao, Y. & Huang, S.-Y. HNADOCK: a nucleic acid docking server for modeling RNA/DNA–RNA/DNA 3D complex structures. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, W35–W42 (2019).
 91. de Vries, S. J., van Dijk, M. & Bonvin, A. M. J. J. The HADDOCK web server for data-driven biomolecular docking. *Nat. Protoc.* **5**, 883–897 (2010).
 92. Macindoe, G., Mavridis, L., Venkatraman, V., Devignes, M.-D. & Ritchie, D. W. HexServer: an FFT-based protein docking server powered by graphics processors. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **38**, W445–W449 (2010).
 93. RxDock. *rxdock.org* <https://www.rxdock.org/>.
 94. DOCK 6: Impact of new features and current docking performance - Allen - 2015 - Journal of Computational Chemistry - Wiley Online Library.
<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/jcc.23905>.
 95. Salentin, S., Schreiber, S., Haupt, V. J., Adasme, M. F. & Schroeder, M. PLIP: fully automated protein–ligand interaction profiler. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **43**, W443–W447

(2015).

96. AnnapuRNA: A scoring function for predicting RNA-small molecule binding poses. <https://journals.plos.org/ploscompbiol/article?id=10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008309>.
97. Vanommeslaeghe, K. *et al.* CHARMM General Force Field (CGenFF): A force field for drug-like molecules compatible with the CHARMM all-atom additive biological force fields. *J. Comput. Chem.* **31**, 671–690 (2010).
98. Dolot, R. *et al.* Crystal structures of thrombin in complex with chemically modified thrombin DNA aptamers reveal the origins of enhanced affinity. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **46**, 4819–4830 (2018).
99. Xu, G. *et al.* Structure-guided post-SELEX optimization of an ochratoxin A aptamer. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **47**, 5963–5972 (2019).
100. Structural basis of DNA folding and recognition in an AMP-DNA aptamer complex: distinct architectures but common recognition motifs for DNA and RNA aptamers complexed to AMP - PubMed. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/9384529/>.
101. Fan, P., Suri, A. K., Fiala, R., Live, D. & Patel, D. J. Molecular Recognition in the FMN – RNA Aptamer Complex. *J. Mol. Biol.* **258**, 480–500 (1996).

Table 1: All programs currently included in the toolbox. The programs depicted here have been integrated in the toolbox's Python API, allowing for their usage and arbitrary combinations.

Program	Usage	Ref
ViennaRNA	Secondary Structure Prediction	58
NUPACK	Secondary Structure Prediction	59
RNAstructure	Secondary Structure Prediction	60
bpRNA	Secondary Structure Prediction	61
Contrafold-SE	Secondary Structure Prediction	62
MultiRNAFold	Secondary Structure Prediction	63
Contextfold	Secondary Structure Prediction	64
IPknot	Secondary Structure Prediction	65
Eternafold	Secondary Structure Prediction	34
Centroidfold	Secondary Structure Prediction	66
SPOT-RNA	Secondary Structure Prediction	67
mfold	Secondary Structure Prediction	68
QGRS	Assessment of structure elements	69
PQSFinder	Assessment of structure elements	70
X3DNA	Assessment of structure elements	71
DSSR2.0	Assessment of structure elements	72
Gypsum-DL	Small molecule conformer prediction	73
RDKit	Small molecule conformer prediction	74
OpenBabel	Small molecule conformer prediction & format conversions	57
RNAComposer (Web)	Tertiary Structure Prediction	75
SimRNA	Tertiary Structure Prediction	76
3dRNA2.0	Tertiary Structure Prediction	77
Rosetta (FARFAR2)	Tertiary Structure Prediction	78
SPQR	Tertiary Structure Prediction	79

AlphaFold (Colabfold)	Protein Tertiary Structure Prediction	40
ARES	Tertiary Structure Scoring	38
Rosetta Score	Tertiary Structure Scoring	80
VMD	RNA to DNA mutation	81
Chimera	RNA to DNA mutation	82
X3DNA	RNA to DNA mutation	71
QRNAS	Tertiary Structure Refinement	83
AMBER	Tertiary Structure Refinement	84
AutoDock Vina	NA - ligand docking	85
ZDOCK	NA - ligand docking	86
iDock	NA - ligand docking	87
RLDOCK	RNA - ligand docking	88
HDOCK	NA - protein docking	89
HNADOCK	NA - NA docking	90
HADDOCK	NA - ligand docking	91
Hex	NA - ligand docking	92
RxDock	NA - ligand docking	93
DOCK6.9	NA - ligand docking	94
PLIP	Docking interaction Analysis	95
AnnapuRNA	Docking Scoring	96
AptaNet	Neural Network based scoring of Aptamer - Protein interactions	42
AmberTools	Ligand & Receptor parametrization	28
CGenFF (Selenium)	Ligand parametrization	97
AMBER	MD simulations & Binding Free Energy Estimation	84
NAMD	MD simulations & Binding Free Energy Estimation	27

Table 2: Selected aptamers and targets, as well as the accompanying PDB ID and reference for which the combinations of programs were tested.

Aptamer	Target	PDBID	ref
TBA	Thrombin	6EO6	98
OBA3	Ochratoxin A	6J2W	99
AMPA	AMP	1AW4	100
GTP Aptamer	GTP	2AW4	100
FMN aptamer	FMN	1FMN	101

Figure 1: 3D structure prediction RMSD and CLASH score for the small scale dataset according to three all-atom predicting RNA 3D structure prediction algorithms.

Figure 2: Complex heavy atom RMSD vs solved reference for each combination of programs tested. There were 6 secondary structure prediction programs that were assessed, in tandem with 4 tertiary structure prediction programs, 2 ligand structure prediction programs and 6 docking programs.

Figure 3: Assessing the performance of different pipelines in different scenarios. For the blind scenario (described in the text in detail), the initial input was the aptamer sequence and nucleic acid type, which was converted using X3DNA if needed. For the secondary structure scenario, the secondary structure was extracted from the 3D structure using X3DNA and provided as constraints to 3D structure prediction software. For the tertiary structure scenario, the PDB structure was used after refinement with QRNAS. For the known ligand scenario, the ligand as it is found in the PDB structure was used, sans ionization and for the All scenario, the PDB was subsetting for the aptamer and the target and then docking was performed.

Figure 4: Optimization for the aptamers for AFM1, PenG and Neomycin using the Genetic Algorithm and the integrative approach to choose programs. The normalized score is calculated by dividing each generation's score by the first generation's. This helps to ground all the scores in a similar scale, even if they may be using different types of scores (E.g. AutoDock Vina's ΔG will rarely fall below -9 kcal/mol, whereas HADDOCK's docking score can be < -200).

Figure 5: Computed ΔG minus the reference ΔG , as verified experimentally and converted from Kd through the standard Gibbs Free Energy Equation $\Delta G = -RT \ln K$

